

Gathering real world evidence through the evaluation of decision history

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Abstract. Clinical Practice Guidelines (CPGs) gather latest evidence-based results to guide and support clinicians over the decision-making process to provide best care. Nevertheless, clinical cases may be subject to some biases (understood as non-compliance with CPGs) that can lead to adapt care delivery. In this work an experience-based decision support leaning on the structuration of the Decisional Event concept for tracking and storing each clinical decision is presented. Moreover, a visual analytics tool is provided in order to facilitate the visualization of biases from guideline-based decision support and the identification and inclusion of real-world evidence into the reasoning process by augmenting the knowledge formalized in the implemented guidelines.

Keywords. Decision support system, Clinical practice guidelines, Experience formalization, Decisional event

1. Introduction

Clinical Practice Guidelines (CPGs) gather latest evidence-based results to guide and support clinicians over the decision-making process. Clinicians, policy makers, and payers expect guidelines would standardize clinical practice while making it as personalized as possible. Hence, the objective is to establish some standards in healthcare considering not only what clinicians do but also what scientific evidence supports [1]. Nevertheless, some clinical cases are subject to some biases (understood as non-compliance with CPGs) that can affect care delivery. These variations can come from different sources affecting clinical practice, such as restrictions coming from the patient him/herself, restrictions related to the proposed therapy, or restrictions related to the analyzed clinical parameters (e.g. a patient is not covered by CPGs due to his/her specificity or complexity and hence, there is no optimal clinical recommendation that would promote its clinical success). Clinician-related effects can also produce clinical

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errors, e.g., overconfidence judgement. This effect occurs when clinicians biased their decisions by overestimating the accuracy of their own clinical judgment [2].

In this work we present an experience-based decision support system that allows not only to report non-compliant cases and generate new knowledge from these non-compliant decisions, but also allows to generate “real-world evidence” for future similar clinical cases. For that, a methodology based on the formalization, storage, and reuse of all the decisions made over time is presented. The objective is to be able to measure and evaluate all biases from guideline-based decision support by reporting (i) the compliance rates with CPGs of the decisions made, (ii) the generation of new knowledge from cases that did not comply with guideline specifications and the evaluation of this new knowledge on new cases, and (iii) the evaluation of the clinical performance of the whole process on the basis of patient-reported clinical outcomes. Finally, a visual analytics dashboard is presented to show up at a glance all the generated real-world evidence to be validated and analyzed by the clinician.

2. Measuring biases from the decision-making process

When identifying the different causes of clinical care biases from the recommendations provided in guidelines, we could differentiate several causes such as (i) the difficulty or complexity of the studied clinical case, (ii) some healthcare or patient-related restrictions, and (iii) the reasoning process of clinicians. In the next chapters, we will analyze the main reasons of guideline non-compliance (understood as a bias on the treatment recommended by CPGs) and how to measure and evaluate the clinical performance when using the information gathered from the decisions made over time.

2.1. Causes of guideline non-compliance

Most of the time, clinicians tend to follow the recommendations provided by CPGs as they expose latest and most reliable evidence-based medicine. Nevertheless, implementing guidelines is not always feasible and not all clinicians do know how to proceed in certain clinical situations [3]. The complexity of clinical cases, the severity of the illness, or the health care system inefficiency have been identified as the main causes for clinicians not to comply with CPGs [4]. On the other hand, patient preferences have been shown to influence the decision-making process, even if this is not yet reflected as evidence [5]. Several works have discussed strategies to include this criteria within the guidelines, re-rating the strength of recommendations and the quality of evidence of the already defined criteria or including this knowledge as new criteria to formalize [6].

2.2. Overconfidence

As every effective problem solving, the clinical reasoning process is governed by an intuitive approach together with an analytic approach [7]. Both approaches work together for the optimal decision-making process in every context. Nevertheless, human behavior can break the balance and introduce a bias in the reasoning process due to some reasons generating overconfidence, among others [8]. This effect can change clinicians’ attitude towards a more confident one, making cognitive aspects the most valuable (i.e. their own criteria are considered to be the best ones with no critical

analysis or comparison) and tending to underestimate errors, assuming that they may not occur [9]. Sometimes the clinician is not even conscious of this bias and this remains untracked, as it happens in a low percentage of the studied clinical cases. Hence, tracking and evaluating clinical practice should better identify and prevent misdiagnoses.

2.3. Generating real-world evidence from the decisional history evaluation

In [10] we proposed a Decisional Event (DE) structure to gather all the information related to the decision making process in a processable way, generating an history of all the decisions made over time. This approach concedes two kinds of information evaluation. First, guideline compliance rates can be measured. As we not only gather the recommendations provided by the guidelines but also the final decision made and even the real executed treatment, compliance can be computed, and non-compliant cases tracked to evaluate their performance based on reported outcomes [11]. On the other hand, having all this data over time permits generating real-world evidence by the use of machine learning techniques. These algorithms allow predicting the variables that most influence patients' outcomes and relationships among them for a given treatment in a particular scenario. The results from these analyses should estimate the expected clinical outcomes for new upcoming cases similar to previous treated patients and even more, see if clinicians are self-consistent with the previously made decisions that were biased from the actual evidence.

2.4. Visualization of the Decisional History

To provide all the information stored within the DE in a visual and intuitive way, we designed a visual analytics dashboard (Fig.1). This dashboard allows exploring all the decisions made over time and the compliance rates slanting the information by the most relevant clinical variables or the treatment of interest. Moreover, details about the specific treatment given (e.g. lumpectomy) within a group (e.g. surgery) can be analyzed along with the toxicities or relapses suffered by the patients concerned.

Figure 1. Visualization of decisions made for a sample of 568 patients with breast cancer, filtered by their tumor size and age. Patients are at the diagnosis stage, which explains why surgery and chemotherapy are the treatments mostly proposed.

This visualization gives at a glance all the results of the computation coming from the DE analysis. The scope of this visualization is to easily identify real-world evidence and give insights to clinicians when diagnosing and treating patients. Moreover, using the experience-based decision support they can include this new evidence as new rules that will augment the knowledge contained in the implemented guidelines.

3. Discussion and conclusion

In this work, we have analyzed the main causes of CPG non-compliance and we have proposed experience-based decision support leaning on the structuration of the DE concept for tracking and storing each clinical decision. Moreover, a visual analytics tool was provided in order to facilitate the real-world evidence identification and inclusion into the actual reasoning process by augmenting the knowledge formalized in the implemented guidelines. Our approach is expected to promote a more reliable and compliant care by a continuous gathering and evaluation of information and clinical performance in every clinical decision-making process.

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References

- [1] S. H. Woolf, R. Grol, A. Hutchinson, M. Eccles, and J. Grimshaw, 'Potential benefits, limitations, and harms of clinical guidelines', *BMJ*, vol. 318, no. 7182, pp. 527–530, Feb. 1999.
- [2] D. J. Miller, E. S. Spengler, and P. M. Spengler, 'A meta-analysis of confidence and judgment accuracy in clinical decision making.', *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, vol. 62, no. 4, pp. 553–567, 2015.
- [3] S. Quaglini, M. Stefanelli, A. Cavallini, G. Micieli, C. Fassino, and C. Mossa, 'Guideline-based careflow systems', *Artificial Intelligence in Medicine*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 5–22, Sep. 2000.
- [4] A. G. Ellrodt, 'Measuring and Improving Physician Compliance with Clinical Practice Guidelines: A Controlled Interventional Trial', *Annals of Internal Medicine*, vol. 122, no. 4, p. 277, Feb. 1995.
- [5] C. A. Umscheid, 'Should Guidelines Incorporate Evidence on Patient Preferences?', *J Gen Intern Med*, vol. 24, no. 8, pp. 988–990, Aug. 2009.
- [6] T. van der Weijden *et al.*, 'How to integrate individual patient values and preferences in clinical practice guidelines? A research protocol', *Implement Sci*, vol. 5, p. 10, Feb. 2010.
- [7] D. Wedding and D. Faust, 'Clinical judgment and decision making in neuropsychology', *Arch Clin Neuropsychol*, vol. 4, no. 3, pp. 233–265, Jan. 1989.
- [8] P. Croskerry and G. Norman, 'Overconfidence in Clinical Decision Making', *The American Journal of Medicine*, vol. 121, no. 5, pp. S24–S29, May 2008.
- [9] E. S. Berner and M. L. Graber, 'Overconfidence as a Cause of Diagnostic Error in Medicine', *The American Journal of Medicine*, vol. 121, no. 5, pp. S2–S23, May 2008.
- [10] N. Muro *et al.*, 'Augmenting Guideline Knowledge with Non-compliant Clinical Decisions: Experience-Based Decision Support', in *Innovation in Medicine and Healthcare 2017*, vol. 71, Y.-W. Chen, S. Tanaka, R. J. Howlett, and L. C. Jain, Eds. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2018, pp. 217–226.
- [11] N. Muro, N. Larburu, J. Bouaud, and B. Séroussi, 'Weighting Experience-Based Decision Support on the Basis of Clinical Outcomes' Assessment', *Stud Health Technol Inform*, vol. 244, pp. 33–37, 2017.